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MODERN APPROACHES TO DIAGNOSIS AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF MEDIASTINAL TUMORS (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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ABSTRACT

The article provides a literature review on the modern approach to diagnosis and surgical treatment of mediastinal tumors. It is noted that despite the progress in diagnostics and minimally invasive surgery, mediastinal tumors require a more detailed and personalized approach. There are still many controversies and uncertainties in the diagnosis and treatment of thymus tumors. Large-scale prospective and randomized studies are lacking, which hinders the creation of high-quality guidelines.

Keywords: mediastinal tumors, diagnosis, surgical treatment, literature review

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СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ДИАГНОСТИКЕ И ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОМУ ЛЕЧЕНИЮ ОПУХОЛЕЙ СРЕДОСТЕНИЯ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье приведен обзор литературы, касающийся современного подхода к диагностике и хирургическому лечению опухолей средостения. Отмечается, что несмотря на прогресс в диагностике и малоинвазивной хирургии, опухоли средостения требуют более детализированного и персонализированного подхода. В диагностике и лечении опухолей тимуса все еще много противоречий и неясностей. Отсутствуют крупномасштабные

проспективные и рандомизированные исследования, что мешает созданию высококачественных руководств.

Ключевые слова: опухоли средостения, диагностика, хирургическое лечение, обзор литературы

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КЎКС ОРАЛИҒИ ЎСМАЛАРИНИ ТАШХИСЛАШ ВА ЖАРРОХОХЛИК ДАВОЛАШДА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ЮНДАШУЛАР (АДАБИЁТЛАР ШАРХИ)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада кўкс оралиғи ўсмаларини ташхислаш ва жарроҳлик даволашга замонавий ёндашувга оид адабиётлар таҳлили келтирилган. Таъкидланишича, ташхислаш ва минимал инвазив жарроҳликда эришилган ютуқларга қарамай, кўкс оралиғи ўсмалари янада батафсил ва шахсийлаштирилган ёндашувни талаб қилади. Тимус ўсмаларини ташхислаш ва даволашда ҳали ҳам кўплаб қарама-қаршиликлар ва ноаниқликлар мавжуд. Кенг миқёсли истиқболли ва рандомизацияланган тадқиқотлар сони, бу эса юқори сифатли кўрсатмаларни яратишга тўсқинлик қилмоқда.

Калит сўзлар: кўкс оралиғи ўсмалари, ташхислаш, жарроҳлик даволаш, адабиётлар шарҳи

Introduction. Mediastinal tumors are neoplasms that arise in the space between the sternum, spine, and lungs, comprising 3-7% of all tumors, of which 60-80% are benign and 20-40% are malignant. These tumors occur equally often in men and women aged 20-40 years. Malignant tumors are characterized by morphological diversity and can threaten vital organs, posing technical challenges during surgical removal, making them one of the complex issues in thoracic surgery.

Anatomically, the mediastinum is bounded by the sternum anteriorly, the spine posteriorly, the mediastinal pleura laterally, and the diaphragm inferiorly. Important structures located here include the thymus, superior vena cava, aortic arch and its branches, lymph nodes, esophagus, pericardium, and others. Fifty percent of mediastinal tumors are localized in the anterior compartment, most commonly thymomas, teratomas, thyroid goiters, and lymphomas. The middle compartment usually includes congenital cysts, while the posterior compartment harbors neurogenic tumors such as schwannomas. From a surgical standpoint, the distribution of lymph nodes into nine regions according to the recommendations of ITMIG and IASLC is important.

Despite advances in diagnosis and minimally invasive surgery, mediastinal tumors require a more detailed and personalized approach. There are still many contradictions and uncertainties in the diagnosis and treatment of thymic tumors. Large-scale prospective and randomized studies are lacking, hindering the development of high-quality guidelines.

Epidemiology, Etiopathogenesis, and Classification of Mediastinal Tumors.

Although mediastinal tumors, especially non-neuroendocrine epithelial tumors of the thymus (TET), are relatively rare, posing challenges for extensive epidemiological studies, research in this direction is constantly conducted and remains highly relevant. This is associated not only with the increasing incidence but also with the continuous updating of new classification criteria for these tumors.

For instance, Gerber T.S. and colleagues [3] conducted a comprehensive analysis of these tumors in the United States and Germany from 1999 to 2019. An epidemiological analysis was performed using the Surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Results (SEER) registry and the database of the Center for Cancer Registration, involving 478 patients aged 0-19 years and 17,459 patients over 20 years diagnosed with malignant tumors of the anterior mediastinum. The authors noted that among patients aged ≥ 20 years, TETs were the most common tumors of the anterior mediastinum (USA/Germany: 63%/64%), followed by lymphomas (14%/8%), while in patients < 20 years old, the predominant tumors were germ cell tumors (42/14%), lymphomas (38/53%), and TETs (10/27%). The overall annual incidence of thymoma was 2.2/2.64 (USA/Germany) per million inhabitants, and thymic carcinoma was 0.48/0.42. The male-to-female ratio was 1:1.09/1.03, with a mean age of $59.48 \pm 14.89/61.33 \pm 13.94$. Patients with thymomas, but not thymic carcinomas, had a significantly increased risk of developing secondary malignant neoplasms by 21%/29% compared to the control group with non-thymic primary tumors [3].

M. Omasa and colleagues [4] utilized the Japanese Association for Research on the Thymus (JART) database to identify 2835 patients from 32 Japanese institutions from 1991 to 2010, of which 1265 patients were examined: 155 cases of thymic cancer (12.3%) and 1110 cases of thymoma (87.7%). Eight hundred and ninety-five (70.8%) were at stage II, and 370 (29.2%) were at stage III. The authors emphasized the importance of conducting epidemiological studies to determine strategies aimed at early detection of malignancy in the thymus and the implementation of rational therapeutic measures [4].

Continuing these JART studies in Japan, M. Okumura and colleagues [5] analyzed the results of surgical treatment of TETs and clarified the significance of prognostic factors, noting that the 10-year survival rates according to TNM classification I, II, IIIA, IIIB, IVA, and IVB were 98.7%, 76.8%, 85.0%, 68.9%, 66.2%, and 59.8%, respectively. T factor, M factor, and tumor size were independent prognostic factors both in cases of thymoma and thymic carcinoma, while the N factor tended to be a prognostic factor in thymoma but not in cases of thymic carcinoma [5].

Regarding the etiopathogenetic features of mediastinal tumors, they mostly reflect the morphofunctional state of target organs. For example, the anterior mediastinum contains the thymus, adipose tissue, and lymph nodes, corresponding to the most common etiology of associated primary tumors. Despite two-thirds of mediastinal neoplasms being benign, approximately 59% of tumors in the anterior compartment are malignant, predominantly epithelial tumors [1, 2].

As shown above, thymoma is the most commonly encountered anterior mediastinal formation in the adult population, although it accounts for less than one percent of malignant neoplasms in adults [6]. Benign thymic formations are rare and include thymolipomas, characterized by fatty composition, and thymic cysts. Thymic cysts can be congenital, representing remnants of the thymopharyngeal duct, or acquired, as manifestations of inflammatory neoplasms such as Hodgkin's lymphoma.

Thymic formations can rarely manifest as aggressive and invasive neoplasms in the form of thymic carcinoma and thymic carcinoid. It should be noted that thymic formations require differentiation from thymic hyperplasia, which in turn is subdivided into true and lymphoid (follicular) types. True thymic hyperplasia is defined as an enlarged thymus with preservation of its original shape and usually occurs under stress conditions such as chemotherapy, burns, and corticosteroid administration. Lymphoid thymic hyperplasia results from an increase in the number of lymphoid follicles in the gland and is associated with autoimmune diseases such as myasthenia gravis [1, 2].

A separate group comprises so-called germ cell tumors, containing primitive germ cells that fail to migrate fully during embryonic development. Although germ cell tumors primarily arise in the gonads, they account for 15% of all anterior mediastinal tumors [1, 2].

The most common germ cell tumors are benign teratomas, which, by definition, contain tissues from at least two of the three germ layers. Benign teratomas mostly contain ectodermal tissue such as hair and teeth but can also contain tissues derived from mesoderm and endoderm, such as bone and intestinal epithelium. If a teratoma contains embryonal or neuroendocrine tissue, it is classified as immature and malignant with an unfavorable prognosis [1, 6].

Seminomas and non-seminomatous germ cell tumors are rarely malignant and typically manifest as bulky, large, lobulated formations. Seminomas account for 25 to 50% of malignant germ

cell tumors. Non-seminomatous germ cell tumors include yolk sac tumors, teratoma with malignant transformation, embryonal carcinomas, choriocarcinomas, and mixed germ cell tumors. These tumors are classically associated with elevated levels of alpha-fetoprotein (AFP) and human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) [1, 6].

Primary mediastinal lymphomas constitute 10% of all mediastinal lymphomas. Hodgkin lymphoma accounts for 50% to 70% of primary lymphomas and is subdivided into nodular sclerosis (most common), lymphocyte-rich, lymphocyte-depleted, and mixed cellularity subtypes. Non-Hodgkin lymphoma constitutes 15% to 25% of primary lymphomas, the most common of which are diffuse large B-cell lymphoma, also known as mediastinal large B-cell lymphoma, and lymphoblastic lymphoma [6].

Another reason for the formation of the anterior mediastinum is mediastinal goiter. Mediastinal goiter typically occurs when the lower part of the thyroid lobes protrudes into the thoracic inlet. Less commonly, mediastinal goiter consists of remnants of embryonic tissues. Other, even less common causes of anterior mediastinal neoplasms include parathyroid adenomas, hemangiomas, and sarcomas [7, 8].

Fibrosing mediastinitis, characterized by progressive infiltration of fibrous tissue, is another unusual cause of anterior mediastinum formation. The etiology of fibrosing mediastinitis includes infections such as tuberculosis and histoplasmosis, as well as reactions to autoimmune syndromes, drugs, and radiation [5, 7, 9].

Despite being even rarer, tumors of the middle and posterior mediastinum are of particular interest from a surgical point of view, including bronchogenic cysts (small benign cysts usually filled with fluid or mucus), mediastinal lymphadenopathy, and tracheal tumors. In most Western thoracic surgical societies, esophageal diseases and lesions of the thoracic aorta are also included in this group. In post-Soviet countries, these pathologies continue to be considered with a focus on narrow specialization, which, in our view, is a more optimal approach, considering the considerable percentage of esophageal diseases and isolated cases of thoracic aorta pathology [6].

Formations of the posterior mediastinum are predominantly represented by neurogenic tumors, including tumors of the nerve sheath, ganglioneuromas, and paragangliomas, most of which are benign. These tumors may have dumbbell-shaped forms, spreading into the spinal canal, exclusively paraspinal, or apical tumors spreading into the cervical region [5, 7, 8].

Features of the clinical course, symptom complexes and syndromes of mediastinal neoplasms.

Occasionally, the diagnosis of a mediastinal neoplasm is incidentally discovered, although in 60% of patients, symptoms manifest upon careful history taking. Symptoms are divided into localizing and systemic [2]. Cough is the most common localizing symptom, occurring in 60% of cases. Among other common obstructive symptoms, chest pain, dyspnea, hoarseness, hemoptysis, and dysphagia can be highlighted. Germ cell tumors may compress the superior vena cava, leading to various symptoms, including periorbital edema and anhidrosis [1, 2].

Paraneoplastic syndromes, especially myasthenia, can manifest in anterior mediastinal tumors. From 30 to 50% of patients with thymoma have myasthenia, while 10% to 15% of patients with myasthenia have thymoma. Nonspecific symptoms of anemia, such as fatigue, may indicate pure red cell aplasia [1, 2, 5].

Hypogammaglobulinemia and predisposition to recurrent infections may also indicate certain types of tumors. The rapid onset of symptoms may indicate an aggressive tumor, whereas a more indolent course may represent a slowly growing tumor [1, 2, 7].

Bronchial breathing above the thoracic vertebrae and gynecomastia may also be signs of specific tumors. The localization of cancer and its composition are crucial for narrowing the differential diagnosis. Biopsy may be unreliable and, in some cases, unnecessary. Tests for diagnosing and assessing mediastinal cancer include the following [2, 8].

The clinical presentation of mediastinal neurogenic tumors may be nonspecific. The specific and most common sign of neurogenic tumors is Horner's syndrome. In most cases, an asymptomatic course is characteristic of tumors in this group. The symptoms and syndromes of mediastinal tumors are determined by their characteristics and interactions with surrounding tissues and organs [8].

Diagnostic criteria for verifying pathological formations in the mediastinum.

As is known, radiological imaging of the chest organs plays an important role in assessing the condition of not only the lungs and mediastinum, but is also the main way to verify neoplasms of the anterior and posterior mediastinum [10-15]. According to a number of researchers, computed tomography (CT) of the chest organs using contrast is the most effective method of radiological assessment, since it allows you to see the specific characteristics of various tissues [10, 11]. For example, thymoma on CT sections usually looks like a slightly heterogeneous mass with smooth or lobular edges, while teratoma is often recognized as a cystic formation containing various components, such as fat, soft tissues and calcifications [6, 13].

According to S. Juanpere et al. (2013), CT helps not only to characterize lesions, but also to determine the stage of pathological processes. Thus, an increase in mediastinal lymph nodes requires special attention. The presence of pleural or pericardial effusion on chest imaging also requires evaluation, as it may be a clue to the diagnosis of lymphoma or non-seminomatous germ cell tumors [6]. Of interest are studies analyzing risk factors for invasion of various mediastinal organs obtained using multislice CT. For example, Y.H. Ma et al. (2023) analyzed prognostic factors and risk of invasion of large mediastinal vessels in thymic tumors. The study included 122 patients with TET confirmed by histopathological analysis. Based on the degree of tumor adjacency to large mediastinal vessels, arterial invasion was divided into grades I, II, and III (<25%, 25-49%, and $\geq 50\%$, respectively); venous invasion was divided into grades I and II (<50% and $\geq 50\%$). According to logistic regression analysis, male patients and pericardial or pleural invasion were independent predictors of 25% arterial invasion. Midline location and mediastinal lymphadenopathy were independent predictors of 50% arterial invasion. For 50% venous invasion, risk factors included midline location, maximum tumor diameter greater than 5.9 cm, and pericardial or pleural effusion. These CT characteristics are considered to be independent predictors of arterial or venous invasion $\geq 50\%$ [14].

Positron emission tomography-computed tomography (PET-CT) is a more useful method for lymphoma staging, as it is more accurate in detecting both intranodal and extranodal disease than CT [13]. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is not always a necessary part of the examination, but is useful in some cases, such as distinguishing thymic hyperplasia from thymic malignancy. MRI is indicated when CT findings are equivocal. Recently, special MRI applications have been developed to accurately identify the tissue components of mediastinal masses. Excellent soft tissue contrast makes MRI an ideal tool for the evaluation of mediastinal cancer. Chemical shift MRI helps to distinguish normal thymus and thymic hyperplasia from thymic cancer and lymphoma [12].

Diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is another special application that reveals minute biophysical and metabolic differences between tissues and structures. The mean apparent diffusion coefficient for mediastinal malignancies can be significantly lower than for benign diseases [6, 9]. Despite the maximum detailing of mediastinal lesions in radiological imaging methods, perioperative pathological diagnosis remains important and often necessary to confirm the suspected diagnosis and choose the optimal treatment method. The choice of biopsy method depends on the location of the lesion, clinical factors such as the age and condition of the patient, as well as the availability of special methods, the necessary specialist and equipment [11, 15]. I.K. Skretting et al. (2022) conducted a retrospective study of all mediastinal biopsy procedures from April 2015 to August 2019. The study included 48 procedures performed in 45 patients (29 men and 16 women) with an average age of 60.5 years. The authors found a significant ($p = 0.006$), moderate and high association between the localization of the anatomical section and the histopathological diagnosis of tumors selected for percutaneous CT-guided biopsy. The largest number of malignant neoplasms was observed in the anterior section [11]. The most promising direction today, especially developed in university hospitals in China, is the use of machine learning models or artificial intelligence to differentiate patients with mediastinal neoplasms that require either direct surgical intervention or preliminary puncture biopsy [15, 16, 17].

Prognosis and results of surgical treatment of mediastinal tumors.

Today, surgical treatment of mediastinal tumors is gaining increasing support. Key issues discussed include multimodal approaches, expansion of minimally invasive techniques, and the use of artificial intelligence for diagnosis and prognosis [18-23].

A study by Takenaka et al. (2023) analyzed the results of surgery after induction therapy in 646 patients. They found that resection of surrounding organs such as the lungs and pericardium had become a common practice. Postoperative complications varied, but perioperative mortality remained low. The authors concluded that the success of surgical treatment of mediastinal tumors depends on a thorough assessment of the indications for surgery [18].

According to Wagner et al. (2021), surgical resection with R0 resection is key to the successful treatment of early-stage TET. However, optimal treatment strategies for patients with locally invasive disease require further research to clarify [19].

W. Qi and H. Tian (2023) highlighted the uncertainty in the role of surgery for advanced mediastinal tumors, calling for a multidisciplinary approach based on chemotherapy. They conducted a retrospective cohort study that confirmed that surgery has a beneficial effect on partial stage IVA patients [20].

A study by Y. Nabe et al. (2024) discusses the prospects of surgical treatment of thymic tumors using immune complex inhibitors. The authors believe that surgery will be a more effective option in cases of questionable resectability as part of a multidisciplinary treatment [21].

R. Lal Chowdhary et al. (2023) presented the largest experience of surgical treatment of thymomas in India. The study was conducted on 119 patients with thymoma within a single clinic. The average age of patients was 52.17 years. Surgery was performed in 64 patients, and radiation therapy was used in 57 patients. The authors concluded that the judicious use of radiation therapy and chemotherapy can increase tumor resectability and improve survival rates [23].

The study by K. Zhao et al. (2024) included 353 patients with type B thymoma from 2012 to 2021. The median follow-up period was 58 months. The 10-year progression-free survival was 91.8%. The authors developed a nomogram model that included R0 resection status and Masaoka stage as prognostic factors for disease progression [22].

O. A. Alexandrova (2021) notes that the complication rate after surgical removal of a mediastinal tumor is 13%. In-hospital mortality was 2.9%. The main reason for diagnostic and treatment errors is the choice of an inadequate biopsy method and surgical approach [24]. Although thoracoscopic surgery is actively developing, there remains a debate about the choice between invasive and open surgery. X. Yin et al. (2024) evaluated the clinical effectiveness of subcostal thoracoscopy and median sternotomy. They concluded that subcostal thoracoscopy is not inferior to median sternotomy as a surgical approach for thymoma resection and lymphadenectomy [25]. Currently, open surgical interventions continue to be one of the main methods of treatment, including various types of sternotomies and thoracotomies. On the other hand, the development of medical technologies has led to an expansion of the use of minimally invasive methods in mediastinal surgery. The main goals of such operations include complete tumor removal, reduction of clinical symptoms and minimization of complications.

Conclusion.

Despite the great progress in diagnostics and minimally invasive surgery, mediastinal tumors require a more detailed and personalized approach. There are still many controversies and uncertainties regarding the diagnostics and treatment of thymus tumors. There is still a lack of large-scale prospective and randomized clinical trials to obtain high-quality evidence and add practice to the guidelines. Screening methods for diagnosing posterior mediastinal masses continue to be multispiral CT and MRI with intravenous contrast, which allow not only to detect the tumor, but also to determine the degree of infiltration and invasion into surrounding tissues and organs. There are also a number of controversial issues related to the choice of open surgical access in complex cases, the choice of tactical and technical approaches to video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery for locally advanced thymus tumors, the volume of lymph node dissection, the appropriateness of neoadjuvant therapy and operations to minimize the volume of intervention, with tactics in the development of surgical complications and tumor recurrence.

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